

THE ATTITUDE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS TOWARDS READING

¹Ximmataliyev Dustnazar Omonovich, ²Gulhayo Umarova Murodiljonovna

¹Professor of the Faculty of Pedagogy of Chirchik State Pedagogical University

²Teacher of the Faculty of Primary Education of Chirchik State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7637982>

Abstract. *The article provides information about the learning activity, interest and mobility of children of junior school age, factors affecting the improvement of their intellectual development, interests of students, the development of intellectual development and its importance.*

Keywords: *intellectual development, improvement, student, junior school age, interest, study, task, moral quality, independent thinking, competence and skill.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, it is required to educate intellectually developed and talented young people who will serve for the development and prosperity of our country. Therefore, without perfecting the educational process, it is impossible to form the youth required by the society.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In pedagogical education, a lot of methods and ways are being developed to find a solution to this, to attract the interest and attention of pupils. Each child and pupil accepts this process differently based on their interests, abilities, and lifestyle. We can take the position of the pedagogue as the main basis in this actual issue.

Research has shown that there are several effective approaches to increasing the interest of young pupils in reading:

- creating a favorable psychological environment for pupils to develop interest in learning.
- development and implementation of a method and a system of methods that increase pupils' interest in learning.
- use of methods aimed at increasing interest in learning among young pupils.
- conducting diagnostics of interest in learning at the initial stage of research
- re-diagnosing the pupils at the end of the final.

There are a number of factors that increase the interest of young students:

the content of the educational material,

the ability of the teacher to convey information correctly,

taking into account personal qualities and individual characteristics

DISCUSSION

In addition, according to G.I. Crosley, motivating pupils during the lesson, giving them motivation for science plays an important role in attracting the attention of the pupil to education.

The initial period of school life covers the age range from 6-7 to 10-11 years (grades 1-4). At primary school age, children have significant reserves of development. Their identification and effective use is one of the main tasks of developmental and educational psychology. When a child enters school, under the influence of education, all his conscious processes begin to be

reconstructed, they acquire qualities characteristic of adults, because children are introduced to a new activity and system of interpersonal relations for them. In order to skillfully use the resources available to the child, it is necessary to adapt children to work at school and at home as soon as possible, teach them to study, be attentive, and work hard. By entering school, a child should have sufficiently developed self-management, work skills, the ability to communicate with people, and role-playing behavior. From the moment the child enters school, a new social situation of development is established. The teacher becomes the center of the social situation of development. At the primary school age, educational activities take the leading place. Educational activity is a special form of students' activity aimed at changing oneself as an educational subject. At primary school age, thinking becomes the main task. Young school children, like preschoolers, usually have a good mechanical memory. Many of them mechanically memorize primary school educational texts during study, which often leads to significant difficulties in secondary school, when the material becomes more complex and larger in size, and solving educational problems requires not only the ability to repeat the material. An age-related feature is also the lack of general will: a young student does not yet have much experience in long-term struggle for the intended goal, overcoming difficulties and obstacles. He may give up in case of failure, lose faith in his own strength and impossibility. Often there is capriciousness, stubbornness. Their usual reason is the lack of family education. The child was used to having all his wishes and demands met, he did not see rejection in anything. Stubbornness and wantonness are a specific form of the child's protest against the strict requirements of the school, the need to sacrifice what he wants. A characteristic feature of the relationship between junior high school students is that their friendship, as a rule, is based on common external life circumstances and random interests; for example, they sit at the same desk, live next to each other, are interested in reading or drawing... The minds of young schoolchildren have not yet reached the level of choosing friends based on any important personality traits. But in general, children of the III-IV grades are more deeply aware of certain qualities of personality and character. And already in the III grade, if necessary, choose classmates for joint training. About 75% of third graders motivate their choices by certain moral qualities of other children.

RESULT

Diagnosis of raising the interest of young pupils. According to the dictionary, "interest" is a great desire to pay attention to something, to know and understand. Cognitive interest is such a type of understanding that has a special place in the life of young pupils. After all, the main focus at school is on understanding the learning system. It follows that "cognitive interest" is a special, personal type of interest in learning.

In order to evaluate the development of interest in teaching of junior schoolchildren, the levels of formation of interest in teaching have been determined. They are listed in the table below.

Level	Feature
High	At this level, the high interest of young pupils in studying; The presence of positive emotions in solving tasks; Actively applying existing knowledge in practice; In certain difficult situations, the pupil does not give up, on the contrary, he uses his brain.
Middle	At this level, pupils' interest in reading is average. This

	<p>interest is described as follows.</p> <p>Insufficiently high form of cognitive interest;</p> <p>The need to constantly awaken the child's attention;</p> <p>The presence of interest in the task and the desire to achieve a certain result;</p> <p>Maintaining certain positive feelings for the proposed profession;</p> <p>The presence of a feeling of satisfaction from a successful and correctly performed work;</p> <p>Pupils feel helpless in certain challenging situations and need help from adults.</p>
Low	<p>At this level, it means that the pupil's learning is low. This interest is described as follows</p> <p>Interest in the lesson only at the beginning;</p> <p>An attitude that can be characterized as "indifference" to the solution of the task;</p> <p>The lack of certain productivity at work, the child's quick distraction.</p>

The following methods have been used to determine the initial level of interest in teaching young students.

1. Methodology for diagnosing educational motivation of young pupils. "Staircase of Motifs" N.V. Elsimova
2. "Motivation Questionnaire" author E.N. Elsimova
3. A comprehensive system for diagnosing cognitive interest in the structure of general learning ability. E. A. Baranov

After the diagnosis, it is possible to come to the conclusion that the level of interest in reading is low among younger pupils. This problem can be caused by a number of factors, including:

- the pupil's attitude towards the teacher;
- the attitude of the teacher to the pupil;
- the importance of science in the pupil's life;
- level of intellectual development of the pupil;
- productivity of educational activities;
- misunderstanding the purpose of training;
- fear of school.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the thoughts and opinions of the third grade students differ from the thoughts and opinions in terms of their content, form, and structure. The reason for this is that the scope of their life experience is wider, and there are also differences in the way they look at things differently, different approaches, and the way they reveal the essence of the problem. By applying all recommendations in practice, you can increase pupils' interest in knowledge. A child's acceptance of scientific information is a more complex process. Therefore, professional help of the teacher is needed here, it is necessary to have the right approach and the maximum involvement of the child in the learning process, besides, to attract the child's attention and

increase his interest. For this, it is necessary to have a well-planned lesson plan, to arm the teacher with new interactive methods and to involve the pupil during the lesson. The pupil must participate in the process willingly and not have a chance to get bored. A child's first step after pre-school education is the place of school. A child who plays and laughs now has a little more responsibility. A game program is pushed from the child's mind and imagination, and the process of acquiring knowledge, working on oneself, and creating new skills takes place. The period of literacy training is a somewhat more complicated period for both the young pupil and the teacher. More work, enthusiasm, endurance is required from the pupil, and patience, perseverance, attention and psychological approach are required from the teacher. In order for the child to successfully pass this process, we teachers are required to have high skills, inquisitiveness, creativity, work on oneself, and organize lessons based on new technologies. Nowadays, in the era of the development of the Internet and virtuality, our study of various sources of information, such as online courses, webinars, marathons, and master classes, which are convenient for us, and our application of them in practice, allow us to master the subject at a perfect level, create an opportunity for pupils and teacher. We can't even say that the pupils' attitude to the lesson in modern education is at a satisfactory level. Because as time progresses, the outlook of young people is also expanding. It is young children who face problems in acquiring the necessary knowledge and skills. What are these problems? The pedagogue's lack of in-depth knowledge of his subject, his inability to use new technologies, Internet networks, and programs, the course of the lesson conducted on the basis of old interpretation methods. Taking this opportunity, I would like to quote the words of the former President I. A. Karimov. " If we want to live well, we need to get rid of evils of old age and vices as soon as possible," he said. Because these words are not in vain, for the development of our country, it is necessary to abandon the old system, to strive for the new, to do more work on ourselves, to awaken the enthusiasm of young people for education and learning. For this, it is necessary to study methodological manuals of foreign pedagogues, research works of Russian scientists, theoretical knowledge, and be able to apply them in practice. Only then will it be possible to interest young children in reading. It is possible to attract the pupil's attention using several methods in the organization of the lesson. For example, spider web method, fan method, four side method, cluster, letter, bee and many similar methods can be studied and worked on. Trust that these methods attract the attention of young people, develop their mental activity, encourage them to think creatively. When we use these methods, we also conduct the lesson in the style of a game, which arouses the interest of the pupils in the lesson. A number of changes and reforms related to education are being carried out in the State Education system from year to year. For example, conditions for learners, smart textbooks, audio-video clips on the topic of the lesson are being developed, new technologies and methods are being introduced to enlighten children on this topic.

REFERENCES

1. Umarova Gulhayo Murodiljonovna. Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarni o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshiruvchi texnologiyalar // American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. Volume 09, Oct., 2022. pp. 210-224.

2. Gulhayo Umarova Murodiljanovna, Zulayho Jabborova Mansur qizi. Kichik maktab yoshidagi o‘quvchilarda o‘qishga bo‘lgan qiziqishini oshirish // “Ustozlar uchun” fidoyi va jonkuyar pedagoglar jurnali. 34-son, 1-to‘plam, dekabr, 2022. 8-12 b.
3. Gulhayo Umarova Murodiljanovna, D.O.Ximmataliyev. O‘smirlarda vatanparvarlik tuyg‘ularini shakllantirishning usullari va vositalari // “Ustozlar uchun” fidoyi va jonkuyar pedagoglar jurnali. 34-son, 1-to‘plam, dekabr, 2022. 13-23 b.
4. Umarova Gulhayo Murodiljanovna. Kichik maktab yoshidagi o‘quvchilarda o‘qishga bo‘lgan qiziqishni klasterli yondashuv asosida rivojlantirish // “Pedagogs” international research journal. Volume-21, Issue-2, November, 2022. Pp.7-10.
5. Musurmonov, R., Khimmataliev, D. O., Sultanova, D. A., qizi Tursunbaeva, Y. R., Khakimova, I. K., & Musurmonova, M. (2023). In the Conditions of New Uzbekistan the Main Issues of Science and Modern Education. *Telematique*, 7686-7694.
6. Nurmatov, S., & Davronov, A. (2022). Practical significance of profiling methods in pedagogical psychodiagnostics. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 1224-1227.
7. Himmataliev, D., & Fayzullaeva, M. (2023). Organization and development of the educational process of educational centers in cluster conditions on the base of digital technologies as a pedagogical problem. *Science and innovation*, 2(B1), 261-264.
8. Umarova, G., & Ximmataliyev, D. (2023). FORMATION OF ATTITUDES TOWARDS LEARNING IN YOUNGER SCHOOL-AGE STUDENTS. *Science and innovation*, 2(B1), 184-186.
9. Khimmataliev, D. O., Elmurzayeva, N. K., Sharakhmatova, A. K., Sotbarov, A. A., Khalmatova, D. A., & Jamoldinova, S. N. (2022). Development Of The Pedagogical (Educational) Cluster In The Regional Educational Space. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 5629-5633.
10. Himmataliyev, D. O., Ashurova, S. Y., & Abduvositova, S. F. (2022). Mavzulararo bog‘lanish klasterini innovatsion didaktik o‘yinlar va mustaqil ishlar orqali rivojlantirish. *integration of science, education and practice. scientific-methodical journal*, 3(9), 120-124.